

Is Facebook a Supportive Social Networking Website in School Life? A case of Grade – X Students in Kathmandu

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Abstract

English medium school students studying in Grade –X were selected to study about the qualities of Facebook. It was aimed to explore whether or not Facebook is helpful to the educational activities of those students. The information gathered through questionnaire has been analysed using mixed method. Based on the review of previous studies and quantitative as well as qualitative information analysis, this study demonstrates that Facebook has qualities of using it in educational activities of high school students. The findings suggest that Facebook needs to be used appropriately to get educational benefits. The literature suggests that the students should be aware of Facebook privacy policy. Proper use of this social networking site keeps them closer and benefits them by sharing information, news and views.

Keywords: Facebook, friendship, education, information, collaborative study

1 Introduction

A number of social network websites are found in use when we just search on three www_s (worldwide web). These sites are popular because of their peculiar features the people can access. When we taken the names of such websites as those of Hotmail messenger, yahoo messenger, gmail chat, google+, Twiter, chaton, viber, Facebook, etc, 'Facebook' is one of the most popular social websites introduced in the USA by Mark Zuckerberg in 2004 (Philips, 2007). According to the online report, Mark had already released many social network websites before he introduced 'The Facebook' while he was a student of Psychology at Harvard University. Two of such websites previously released were 'Coursematch' that was accessible to view people taking their degree and 'Facemash' that used to allow users to rate appearance of people. Philips (ibid) reported that 1200 Harvard students had signed up within 24 hours since he released 'The Facebook', and more than 50% undergraduate students opened their personal account in the first month. Gradually, other universities in Boston, the Ivy League and the other universities excessively used it. It was widely spread throughout the world when it got own unique domain 'www.Facebook.com' in 2005. According to the record of March 2013, more than 1.11 billion had been using 'Facebook' since it was publicly extended beyond the educational institutions in 2006 (Prezi, 2014). In Nepal, about 1.39 million people have been using Facebook that has placed Nepal at 70th position in the world of Facebook users (RDman, February 2014). The record consists of approximately 69% male and 31% female users.

The website allows people or organisations to join and increase earning through advertising revenue. This directly benefits Zuckerberg increase his earning. From his earning, he paid more than a billion dollars in 2012 (Ambord, 2014), which is valued 104 billion for 2013 (Prezi, 2014). It was his fortune that 'Facebook' placed him in the list of top 500 and the youngest CEO at the age of 28 in 2013.

Facebook is taken as a home where someone can deliver message, browse people, collect photos or have a live chat with each other. This has created a ground where we can keep in touch with friends and family wherever we are. It allows people to write comments, tag photos and articles with friends. This also lets Facebook users leave latest information on its status. The users post travel snaps, information, occasional programme information, and so on. In other words, Facebook is an online photo album, which is for fun, games, business, finding old friends, and more (Nations, 2014).

The record of Facebook users shows that the users have been benefited by using this social network site. This is to explore why and how the students make use of this social networking site. Specifically, this study aims to find if it is supportive in the study of the students or in something else.

Purpose of the Study

This is a small scale study on a popular social networking site 'Facebook'. Very specifically the study aims to explore why and how the school students make use of this site. It also tries to find out whether or not 'Facebook' is supportive social networking site in the study of students.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Why do students use Facebook?

The features such as email, bulletin boards, instant messaging, video and picture posting, and downloading functions serve the educational function of enabling communication, collaboration and sharing between students and faculty (Eteokleous, et.al, 2012). They opine that the students use internet for social networking as well as study. Specifically, the students find Facebook a place to get together, collaborate, discuss and exchange information with each other. The research concluded that Facebook promotes their educational interests.

The entire system of Facebook is designed for exploring and engaging several members of the site which allows us to establish connections between heterogeneous people, components and ideas (Ginger, 2008). He opines that Facebook is a source of information, ground of communication, and arena of identity performance. A review of Facebook researches has revealed that Facebook users are motivated by external pressures like birthday, occasion, event, etc and internal features like need for social engagement i.e keep in touch with friends or relatives (Wilson, Gosling & Graham, 2012). The review also reported that the people who were lonely engaged themselves commenting and posting wall posts. A key reason which is promoting social networking sites is the formation of like-minded individuals' group who exchange information (Osterman Research, 2012). The research stated the view of a business consultant that Facebook usually delivers information on expectations and cares individual interests; it is very reliable and friendly, and may be antidote to loneliness. Another research found that chatting on Facebook and posting status updates were taken negatively for high school students whereas checking what the friends were upto and sharing links were considered as positive academic activities (Junco, 2011). They also stated that chat feature provides multitasking facilities and may have direct negative effect on the school work.

2.2 Is it friendly in student life?

The social networking sites can support the students and teachers in their collaborative learning where they can be virtually closer to engage themselves in educational or pedagogical environment in a new and innovative way (Eteokleous, et.al, 2012). They conclude that the social networking sites provide the learners and teachers communication facilities which make sharing information possible. The research about Facebook privacy in 2009 showed that about 60% fresh students of Harvard University created their account within the month they got email address (Jones & Soltren, 2009). The research reported that 70% students shared their personal information like phone, location, interest and social security number. Another research found that 92% of the students spent at least sometimes per day (Junco, 2011). In contrast, a comparative study found that about 55% Facebook users accessed their profile everyday whereas about 60% MySpace users did the same (Dwyer, et.al, 2007). It shows that there were more fans of MySpace than Facebook. According to the report, majority of the students spent about 79 minutes in average and viewed Facebook 5 to 6 times a day. They specially gave time to view photos, comments and status update. Similarly, a research in the US reported that among the Facebook users (students) 54% were female students and 46% were male (Valenzuela, Park & Kee, 2008). This is supported by another research which found that 98.5% students (participants) checked their Facebook everyday (Roberts, 2010). It seems that almost all the students had Facebook profile.

2.3 What are the impacts on student life?

The Facebook users have a risk of keeping their materials safely where this demands a better tool to manage privacy (Liu, 2013). Facebook users at MIT were found to be careful while making friends on Facebook according to Eteokleous, et.al (2012). They reported that 63.45% students did not friend strangers. Only 7.83% students thought that it was beneficial making strangers their friends. This is supported by a research report that concluded those students who spent more time on Facebook chat achieved lower grades in their performance than who just spent time on posting links on Facebook status (Junco, 2011). In contrast, the research found that Facebook chat is very useful for multitask activities that the students and teachers can purposefully utilise for their academic activities.

2.4 What are the challenges in student life?

The study about Facebook privacy reported that maximum students would like to share their information with everyone on their Facebook (Jones & Soltren, 2009). At the same time, it also reported that 62% students in Harvard University did not like to disclose information. Similarly, even if the users would like to keep their information secret, they cannot because information is not private (Boyd, 2008). He says that keeping knowledge private is more difficult than spreading it. On the other hand, Facebook successfully integrates fake profiles into an existing friendship network (Krombholz, Merkl & Weippl, 2012). Golder, Wilkinson and Huberman (2013) argue that physical, academic and social well-being is affected by their choice. They think that choosing a right person as a friend on social networking site eg. Facebook, is the first challenge for students when they get freedom of first time. They suggest that messaging on Facebook is appreciable and reliable feature. Asif and Khan (2012) from their research argue that the Facebook users are not aware of the privacy features although the policies are clearly mentioned on the site. They also found that the users are not familiar with how the personal information can be shared by unauthorised users. This leaks even very confidential information.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The research is guided by mixed method. The research design is grounded on quantitative and qualitative approach. This is based on phenomenological research in which the experiences of Grade -X students are described (Creswell, 2003) to find out the usefulness of Facebook. However, the findings are analysed and interpreted more likely qualitatively. To obtain qualitative and quantitative data, sampling method was chosen considering the economy of time and money as it must be decided at early stage of overall research planning (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007).

3.2 Sampling

Sampling is perhaps the best method of gathering information for any kind of research from the view point of economy of time and money. This study followed non-probability sampling as it is targeted to a particular group i.e Grade – X students (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007). Mainly the researcher selected a city school in which the particular group of students were chosen as informants. Specifically, the convenience sampling (Kothari, 2004) was employed for the study. The convenient school for the researcher in the capital of Kathmandu was selected where the questionnaire was administered to Grade - X students. To gather specific information about Facebook use, its effects and impacts, the study also employed purposive sampling (Kothari, *ibid*). For the purpose, only Grade – X students of a private English medium school were selected as participants. In the group, there were 51 students who were requested to fill up the questionnaire without any hesitation on their own.

3.3 Data Collection Process

A questionnaire is perhaps one of the best tools to gather information. It consists of several questions computerised and printed in a definite order (Kothari, 2004). In almost all the cases, questionnaire is free from the biasness because the participants have freedom of expressing their opinion. Therefore, a structured questionnaire was designed and administered to the participants to get their opinion for this research. To gather information, the researcher distributed the questionnaire to the Grade – X students in their classroom to be filled up then and there. Then the completed questionnaires were collected back from them.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Facebook Access

The expectation before the collection of information was very different than the result produced from through the questionnaire. It was speculated that almost all the participants had their Facebook account but the data showed an unexpected result. Among the 51 students of Grade – X, only 32 students had their Facebook account but 19 of them did not have. It shows that about 63% of tenth graders either ignore Facebook or similar social networking site or are not influenced with its

popularity. It can be imagined that still about 37% of SLC (School Leaving Certificate) students are away from Facebook. This is more likely reflected in the research of Dwyer, et.al, (2007) as they found that there were more people using 'MySpace' than 'Facebook' users.

While analysing the record of total Facebook users i.e 32, it is found that many of them have opened their Facebook at around the same time. Among the Facebook users i.e 32, it is found that 12 (37.5%) students have been using the site for 1 – 2 years whereas 13 (40.62%) students have been using it for 3 – 4 years. Similarly, 2 (6.25%) of them have been using Facebook for more than 4 years. It shows that maximum city school students sign up their Facebook profile in between their 10 – 13 year age. Only 5 (15.6%) students have recently signed up their Facebook profile within this year. Although Facebook policy clearly restricts that below 16 year age none is allowed to sign up profile, this finding proves that students have already signed up their personal profile on Facebook. The participants are all below the restricted age. The following table shows the clear picture of users.

According to the findings of the research, most of the students are influenced by their friends as the finding shows 18 (56.25%) out of 32 have known about Facebook from their friends. Similarly, 9 (28.12%) have heard about Facebook from their family members. Only 1 (3.12%) heard from the teacher. It shows family is also the major source of Facebook or similar social networking site information after their friends. There are 3 (9.37%) students who have come to know about this social networking site from other sources (not TV/radio).

Below 1 year	5	15.62%
1 – 2 years	12	37.5%
3 – 4 years	13	40.62%
Over 4 years	2	6.25%

Table no. 1

The findings show that maximum SLC students have accessed Facebook profile because of their friends whereas their family is also the source of Facebook access. Very few students of Grade – X have been influenced by other sources.

4.2 Frequency of using Facebook

The responses of the students shows that majority of them access their 'Facebook' account once a week as the number of 12 (37.5%) students responded they use Facebook once a week. It may be because of their school study as well as longer hour school time as they express they leave their home to attend their first class at 7 o'clock early in the morning. Second majority of 8 (25%) students signed in their Facebook profile twice a week. Nevertheless, the least number of 2 (6.25%) students used the site daily. The finding is unlike the report of Roberts (2010) but it is assured by the findings of Jones and Soltren (2009). Consequently, there are only 2 (6.25%) students who used the site twice a month but more than this, 6 (18.75%) participants used their Facebook account once a month. The following table reflects the picture clearly.

Daily one hour or more	2	6.25%
Once a week	12	37.5%
Twice a week	8	25%
Once a month	6	18.75%
Twice a month	2	6.25%
Others	2	6.25%

Table no. 2

There are only 2 (6.25%) participants who rarely use their Facebook account. In brief, maximum Grade – X students give sometime once in a week even if they have overload of school work.

4.3 Why do Students use Facebook?

When we study the purpose of releasing social networking sites, the goals clearly inform the world people that the social networking sites are designed for exposing educational information, business motives, sharing ideas and transmitting news but apparently the actual utilisation of them is very different. According to the findings of this study, the highest number 23 (71.87%) students use Facebook for just having a chat with their friends or relatives. Similarly, not very different task, 2

(6.25%) of 32 students just pass time increasing the list of friends on Facebook. This is supported by Wilson, Gosling and Graham (2012) as they view people use Facebook for sharing events like birthday, occasions, etc and to maintain the relationship with friends and relatives with live chat. Unexpectedly, the finding informs that very few i.e only 4 (12.5%) students make use of Facebook for chatting as well as their educational activities. This is more likely the findings of Junco (2011) but unlike the report of Eteokleous, et.al (2012).

Chat with friends/relatives	23	71.87%
Chat/discuss study matters	4	12.5%
Make many friends	2	6.25%
Others	3	9.37%

Table no. 3

According to this research findings and also of Osterman Research (2012), majority of students just use Facebook for exploring like-minded friends who have similar interests. They kill their time by chatting other than about academic matters (Junco, 2011). Although Facebook has been designed for multitask activities, majority of students make this as a platform of sharing personal views on chat (Ginger, 2008) which hampers the grades in their study (Junco, 2011).

4.4 Is it supportive in the study?

The result of the study shows a conflicting argument about the use of Facebook. About 71.87% students spend their time chatting with their friends and relatives. In contrast, almost all the respondents have positive thinking about Facebook use. Out of 32 respondents, 26 (81.25%) students believe that Facebook helps them in their study through which they share information, news and views with their friends and relatives. This assure the view of Eteokleous, et.al (2012) who found that social networking sites provide students and teachers a virtual ground for collaborative learning in innovative way. This is reflected in the following responses of the students:

It is helpful in my study. As I am Grade 10 student, I don't want to hamper my study and waste my time in unnecessary matters but I discuss subject matters with my friends.

Another student says,

'Facebook publishes different news and ideas through which we can increase our knowledge. We can also discuss our study matters with our friends and teachers.'

Similarly, another respondent says,

'If we like the pages of Facebook, they can give various information pertaining to Science, community, country or various singers, actors/actresses, public figures, etc.'

One of the informants says, 'Sometimes we can know about our homework by chatting with our friends and discuss the same.' Yet another respondent views,

'Facebook has become one of the most important sources of information throughout the world. We can exchange and gain knowledge with many people. It has become a place for exploring myself.'

These responses value the usefulness of Facebook that is confirmed by research findings of Ginger (2008). In broader sense, another student expresses, 'Facebook contains overall information about globe. Especially it contains post about political matters so that it helps in Social Studies. Also scientific facts are posted there.' This view is opposing the finding of Junco (2011) although the study of Eteokleous, et.al (2012) supports it.

Is it helpful in your study?		
Yes	No	Both
26	4	2
81.25%	12.5%	6.25%

Table no. 4

There are only 2 (6.25%) respondents who argue with their logics that Facebook can be beneficial if it used properly to share information and ideas but it may spoil their study if it is made the place of just unnecessary chat and posts. Nevertheless, there are 4 (12.5%) students who take Facebook negatively because they think it is just used for unnecessary chat; nobody posts study materials on it.

It can be concluded that there are some grievances of Facebook although the study has found the majority of SLC students using it in a supportive way to their study. However, there is always a corner to doubt this social networking site.

4.5 Is Facebook giving any trouble?

When the responses were analysed thoroughly, the result came out with positive aspects of Facebook. The study has found only a respondent who has experienced some kind of harassment while using Facebook. The student says, 'People use 'if...' words in their chat or messages.' Mostly friends use unsocial language. Although it is minor record among those 32 respondents, apparently it may be an alarming threat in the future endeavour. This is also found in the research of Golder, Wilkinson and Huberman (2013). They think freedom for the first time students get to sign up Facebook is a big challenge for them. The findings here reflect that Facebook can be utilised positively in academic activities or other social functions. In short, fortunately this social networking site has not reached that much to the exploitation of social, cultural and academic environment in the city schools.

Conclusion

When we go through Facebook policy, it is against the law to sign up Facebook profile below 16 years age. Apparently, the analysis of the results has informed that about 63% Grade – X students have already got their Facebook profile whereas there are still 37% high school students away from Facebook. Among the Facebook users, 40.62% students have been found using the site for about 4 years whereas about 37.5% students have used it for about 2 years. Very few but more significant record is that there are 6.25% students who have been using the site over 4 years. It shows that most of the high school students access Facebook at their early age at around 10. At the same time, the majority of students sign in their Facebook profile once (37.5%) or twice (25%) a week. However, the second majority of students use this social networking site once (18.75%) or twice (6.25%) a month.

It is found from the research that the highest number of students (71.87%) uses Facebook just for passing time by chatting with friends and relatives. Unlike this result, only 12.5% students utilise Facebook for their study purposes. Although, they spend their time in unnecessary activities on Facebook, a conflicting result has been found that maximum (81.25%) students believe Facebook can be beneficial for their academic activities. Similarly, it has positive effect in the mind of students because almost all students have fair response using Facebook. In contrast, it has very minor but serious matter the students also face some kind of harassment because of their friends' language. However, Facebook has been accepted to be a supportive social networking site.

Recommendations

Although it is a small scale study, it has produced some remarkable points about Facebook. The study has some limitations too, for the further researches can fill up the gaps. The study is limited to a school case in the capital city Kathmandu. The research could take wider range samples to increase validity and reliability of the study. Only a questionnaire was employed as a tool to collect data. Other methods could be applied for collecting more detail information about Facebook. Further research can be conducted to find the reality of Facebook use and its application in educational activities.

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